

EXPRESSION OF LEGAL TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *There are various studies in the field of jurisprudence devoted to the use of legal terms: laws, legal documents, court hearings, and so on. However, there is little work to study the translation of English legal terms into Russian.*

Key words: *linguists, terminologists, legal terms, justice workers, legal terms, terminological systems*

Currently, the field of law is of particular interest to linguists, in particular, terminologists, due to the development of relations between countries in various fields of activity. Jurisprudence plays an important role and occupies a special place in the life of modern society.

The subtitle of jurisprudence is the language of relevant documents and protocol speeches of justice officials. The terms and formulas used in this case are monosemantic. They have firm and clear meanings and are provided with definitions that can be clearly interpreted in industrial dictionaries, as well as complete interpretations in specialized reference books, texts of laws, and so on.

The legal encyclopedic dictionary defines "legal term" as "an oral expression of state-legal concepts, through which the content of normative-legal instructions of the state is expressed and strengthened."

Lawyers define a legal term as "a word or phrase that is a generalized noun used in legislation". legal understanding, it has a clear and unambiguous meaning and is characterized by semantic uncertainty, functional stability.

Study of legal terminology as well as terminology of other special fields of knowledge

Niy deals with terminology, one of the fields of which is terminological translation. However, the problems of semantics and translation of terms discussed in this article relate to typological and comparative terminology. As noted in the

reviews describing the structure of terminology at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, representatives of these fields are trying to describe the parameters and characteristics of different terminological systems and compare them with each other. Thus, several areas of terminology explore different aspects of the semantics and translation of terms.

As noted in the research on the translation of terminological units, “two groups of terminological problems in the translation of scientific and technical literature are the most important and relevant - the problem of using a special dictionary as an element of distribution. adaptation of terms in a foreign language.

“Lawyer” is the most common word to refer to someone who defends people in court or advises people on legal issues. Lawyers sometimes do legal work related to only one area of law, such as medical work or company law, or they can do general work for different legal matters.

It follows from the definitions that the only difference between the equivalents of the term “lawyer” is that it refers to a particular field. the legal system (especially the English, American, or Scottish legal system), but also in the functions performed by the lawyer. For example, the terms attorney, attorney, and counselor represent the primary responsibility of the attorney in court to represent the rights of the accused or plaintiffs.

It follows that dispersion issues should be given Special attention in translating units belonging to national terminology and terminology systems. The researcher emphasizes the following features of the translation of terms of this group: “Differences in the translation of terms in connection with the development of national terminology in different socio-cultural and historical conditions is an absolutely normal objective phenomenon; in many cases there is no complete equivalence between terms in different languages. Nevertheless, the tendency to add redundant variants to the dictionary, reflecting the occasional use of foreign language terms, poses serious difficulties in the work of a translator.

Given the relevance of the terms discussed above to different national legal systems, another problem to be studied in the theory of terminological translation is the use of transliterated foreign terms rather than in dictionary records. adequate translation. As a rule, terms like lawyer-lawyer are difficult to understand; lawyer; coroner; criminal; crime - a serious crime; misdemeanor - wrong action, sheriff.

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